

Perceptual Quality Assessment of Compressed Volumetric Human Holographic Sequences at Varying Viewing Distances in VR

Mohamad Hjeij^{1,3,*}, Mario Montagud^{2,3}, David Rincón¹, Leonel Toledo³, Sergi Fernández³

¹Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - Barcelona, Spain

²Universitat de València - València, Spain

³i2CAT Foundation - Barcelona, Spain

*Corresponding Author: Mohamad Hjeij (Hjeij.mohamad@i2cat.net)

Abstract— Volumetric video compression is essential for addressing processing and bandwidth challenges, while minimizing perceptual quality loss, in emerging holographic tele-transportation (i.e. holo-transportation) services. Research in this field has primarily focused on compression efficiency and/or on real-time performance, but less attention has been given to the perceptual impact of volumetric video compression when viewing dynamic sequences of human holograms at varying distances in Virtual Reality (VR) scenarios. This paper first provides objective evidence on the promising performance of a novel Video-based Point Cloud Compression Codec (V*-PCC) compared to a state-of-the-art Geometry / anchor octree-based (G-PCC) codec. Then, the V*-PCC codec is adopted to run a user study in which observers view sequences of volumetric holographic user representations at different compression levels, shown at varying distances. The results reveal two key insights: (i) perceptual quality improves at equivalent compression settings as the viewing distance increases; and (ii) compression artifacts become less noticeable and more tolerable at greater distances. These findings not only support the need for further Quality of Experience (QoE) studies but interestingly reinforce the potential of devising dynamic viewport- and position-aware encoding strategies to overcome current scalability and interoperability limitations in this field.

Keywords—Volumetric Video Compression, QoE, viewing distance, quality perception)

I. INTRODUCTION

Volumetric video and holographic technologies are becoming a cornerstone of enhanced immersive experiences. However, remaining challenges must be effectively addressed to achieve successful and widespread adoption, particularly in the context of multiuser services deployed across distributed, ubiquitous, and heterogeneous environments. Volumetric video compression is a fundamental enabling technology to alleviate processing and bandwidth requirements, while minimizing perceptual quality loss. However, research in this field has been primarily focused on optimizing the compression efficiency and/or on real-time performance, but less attention has been given to the perceptual impact when users view dynamic sequences of human holograms with different quality (compression) levels at varying distances in Virtual Reality (VR) scenarios, which are commonplace situations in such an immersive *medium*. Effectively addressing such research question will however help in driving technological advances in this field, fine-tuning

associated systems, and may potentially contribute to scalability, interoperability and sustainability of the derived services.

The research community is aware of the importance of such a topic, and recent works have shed preliminary – yet relevant – light on the impact on the Quality of Experience (QoE) when visualizing volumetric video sequences of dynamic human holograms with different compression levels, when considering diverse key related aspects and/or conditions like:

- Volumetric video formats and variants: Point Clouds [1, 2, 3, 4, 5], comparison among video-based vs geometry-based Point Cloud codecs [6], tile-based Point Cloud encoding and delivery vs non-adaptive baseline strategies, or Point Cloud vs mesh-based representations [5, 7]), etc.
- Impact of geometry and texture distortion for Point Cloud compression [3].
- Dynamic switches between quality levels during a volumetric video sequence [1, 4, 8].
- Diverse viewing modes and conditions, such as: 2D viewing on flat screens (e.g. [1, 7]); immersive VR viewing, using headsets, with 6 Degrees of Freedom or 6DoF (e.g. [2, 3, 4, 5]) and even comparing 3DoF vs 6DoF (e.g. [6]).
- Distance levels between the observer and the target hologram [5, 7, 8].

This paper builds upon previous works on this domain, aiming to shed further light on the impact of viewing distance levels while overcoming observed limitations (or at least complementing existing evidence with further test conditions):

- Existing studies have adopted high-quality volumetric video sequences from an open dataset [9], created with a professional volumetric capture setup. While it contributes to replicability, these sequences have a rather short duration (10s), do not convey conversational content, and might not accurately represent the volumetric captures that can be obtained by using off-the-shelf affordable RGB-D cameras (e.g., Microsoft Azure, Orbbec Femto Bolt) that can be purchased by regular users.

- While the works in [5, 7, 8] have preliminarily assessed the impact of distance levels for volumetric video viewing, such results would be benefited from further research and validation activities, when referred to Point Cloud compression and VR viewing. First, the work in [7] focused on 2D viewing on a flat screen, but not on VR viewing using a headset. Second, the work in [5] focused on the impact on conversion from Point Clouds to meshes for a more effective rendering, enabling 6DoF to users while viewing such sequences (which may impact the generalization and aggregation of results). However, that work only considered the addition of one close and one further hologram in the VR scenario, always with the same quality levels, and did not address Point Cloud compression aspects to assess perceptual differences. Third, the study in [8] already considered 3 viewing distance levels in the evaluation, but it was based on Augmented Reality (AR) – and thus not VR – viewing and, maybe due to the limited Field of View (FoV) of the AR headset, did not show full-body human sequences in all these 3 distances, but just parts of the body in the closest distance levels (face and shoulder, torso)

This paper overcomes these observed limitations and gaps in the state-of-the-art, by:

- Creating high-quality and longer Point Cloud sequences, using 3 Orbbec Femto Bolt RGB-D cameras with color (RGB) resolution and depth (D) resolution of 1080p and 720p, respectively, capturing a user from the frontal viewpoint, performing body gestures in a conversational context.
- Evaluating the impact of compression levels across three distance levels in VR viewing, but without enabling 6DoF to ensure equivalent viewing conditions for all participants, and including different and longer evaluation sequences (although for the same recorded actor) to alleviate the impact of information retention and attention loss, and of insufficient duration to accurately rate the perceived QoE.
- Adopting a combination of Single Stimulus Methodology (SSM) (used in e.g. [1, 4, 6]) and Double Stimulus Methodology (DSM) (used in e.g. [3, 5, 7]) in the evaluation process to maximize reliability of results and potentially being able to correlate results obtained across both methodologies, as this seems to cause debate in the community [3, 6].

After providing initial objective evidence on the promising performance of a novel Video-based Point Cloud Compression Codec (V*-PCC) compared to a state-of-the-art Geometry / anchor octree-based (G-PCC) codec [6, 10], the V*-PCC codec is adopted to run a user study in which observers view sequences of volumetric holographic user representations at different compression levels, shown at varying distances, in immersive VR mode. The results reveal two main insights: (i) perceptual quality improves at equivalent compression settings as the viewing distance

increases; and (ii) compression artifacts become less noticeable and more tolerable at greater distances. On the one hand, these findings support the need for further QoE studies in this domain, in order to accurately find out the compression levels that result in noticeable and/or annoying quality degradations, as a function of the observation distance. On the other hand, these results reinforce the relevance and potential of devising dynamic viewport- and position-aware encoding strategies to address current scalability, interoperability and sustainability needs in this domain.

II. RELATED WORK

As anticipated in Section I, previous studies have assessed quality perception aspects for volumetric video sequences representing humans, in a variety of test conditions and scenarios.

The work in [1] assessed the impact on QoE of switching between quality levels when viewing short (10s) Point Cloud sequences on 2D screens, when delivered via HTTP Adaptive Streaming. It was found that the texture of Point Cloud sequences is an essential aspect to deliver satisfactory QoE, and that content with low contrast differences in the sequences results in enhanced QoE. The work in [2] presents a toolbox to support the preparation and execution of QoE experiments related to visualization of (compressed) Point Cloud sequences in VR environments, supporting 6DoF navigation. The work in [7] subjectively analyzed the impact of compression levels and observation distances for both Point Cloud and mesh-based hologram representations, using short 10-second sequences and 2D screens. Two main findings can be highlighted from [7]: (i) a closer viewing distance leads to a lower QoE for a certain quality level; (ii) Point Cloud compression seems most appropriate for low bit rate budgets, whereas mesh compression seems to be more appropriate when the observation distance is close, and the bit rate can be high. The work in [6] performed a subjective video quality evaluation study in an immersive VR viewing mode, by: (i) comparing 3DoF and 6DoF viewing conditions to understand how interacting in the virtual space affects the perception of quality; and (ii) comparing a video-based vs an anchor octree-based codec. The work in [3] subjectively assessed the effect of geometry and texture distortion in Point Cloud compression, in immersive VR viewing scenarios with 6DoF capabilities. The work in [4] analyzes the impact on QoE when viewing Point Cloud sequences encoded with tile adaptive strategies with respect to a non-adaptive baseline strategy, in immersive VR with 6DoF. Results in [4] confirm considerable gains when using the adaptive tile-based adaptive streaming approach with respect to a non-adaptive approach, while delivering comparable quality levels. The study in [5] assesses the effects of converting Point Cloud to meshes with different quality representations to alleviate the processing requirements needed for efficient Point Cloud rendering, using diverse sequences of a 10-second duration. The results show that, in an immersive VR viewing condition with 6DoF, compression levels (associated to the conversion process) and the observation distance influence the subjective quality perception, but quality switches have a limited influence on

the subjective quality perception. These insights motivate further research in this domain.

Finally, the work in [8] evaluates the impact of four factors on the QoE when visualizing dynamic Point Cloud sequences of a 10-second duration in an AR setting: encoding parameters, quality switches, viewing distance, and content characteristics. The results in that study show that the QoE decreases when applying high compression levels, when switching to lower quality levels, and when the sequences are viewed at a shorter distance, and vice versa. Additionally, the results indicate that users hardly perceive differences between quality levels at high viewing distances.

This study aims to shed further light in this field, by extending its scope and overcoming observed limitations in these earlier and relevant works.

III. METHOD

This study includes two main tests related to volumetric video encoding, applied to dynamic human holographic sequences. Test 1 establishes a baseline comparison between the standard G-PCC codec [6, 10] and a newly proposed V*-PCC codec, which introduces a novel video-based point cloud compression pipeline. Unlike traditional codecs like H.264 or H.265, optimized for 2D color image sequences and based on lossy schemes that degrade 3D spatial fidelity, V*-PCC is designed to address the structural and geometric complexity of point cloud data. The pipeline transforms volumetric content into 2D image representations that encode geometry, later mapped into the color domain. These images can be compressed and decompressed using standard video codecs, enabling efficient streaming and reconstruction with minimal quality loss and artifacts. Test 2, the core contribution of this paper, analyzes the perceptual quality of sequences encoded with V*-PCC as a function of compression level and viewing distance.

A. Test 1: Technical Comparison between G-PCC codec and V*-PCC Pipelines:

Test 1 consists of an objective performance evaluation to compare the G-PCC and V*-PCC codecs, under controlled conditions and across three quality levels: High Quality (HQ), Medium Quality (MQ), and Low Quality (LQ).

Volumetric recordings were captured using three Orbbec Femto Bolt RGB-D cameras, positioned in a frontal arc configuration with approximately 45° spacing to ensure full-body coverage and consistent depth mapping. The setup was calibrated to align color and depth streams spatially, and the recording environment featured controlled lighting to minimize shadows and color inconsistencies. Each sequence was 90 seconds long and featured the same actor performing a series of natural conversational gestures, including hand movements, facial expressions, head turns, and posture shifts chosen to simulate typical interactions in remote presence scenarios. The cameras were synchronized and recorded 1080p color and 720p depth streams at 15 FPS. The encoding for the V*-PCC codec was performed using Constant Rate Factor (CRF) and Quantization Parameter (QP) values of 34 (LQ), 17 (MQ), and 0 (HQ), applied to the color-mapped

geometry representation. Internally, this encoding relies on a standard video codec typically H.264 or a similar format for compressing the texture and geometry streams.

Fig. 1. Resulting visual quality when using G-PCC (left) and V*-PCC (right) for the HQ sequences (bandwidth of 12 Mbps for G-PCC and of 9 Mbps for V*-PCC).

In contrast, the G-PCC codec employed voxel-based quantization with voxel sizes of 0.05 (LQ), 0.025 (MQ), and 0.0 (HQ) to generate geometry-only compressed sequences (Fig. 1). The following metrics were measured in each test condition: (i) Voxel count, which indicates the point density for the encoded sequences; (ii) Encoded Frames per Second (FPS), which is indirectly limited by the capturing FPS; and (iii) Processing time, which represents the time required to encode each frame.

B. Test 2: Subjective Quality Assessment of V*-PCC Across Viewing Distances

Test 2 aimed to subjectively evaluate the perceived quality of dynamic holographic human sequences encoded with V*-PCC, across different compression levels and viewing distances. Each participant evaluated nine test conditions, featuring an actor performing facial and body expressions in a conversational context. Holograms were viewed at three fixed distances: D1 (1 m), D2 (2.5 m), and D3 (5 m). At each distance, a high-quality (HQ) training sequence was shown first, followed by three quality levels (HQ, MQ, LQ) in counter-balanced order. MQ and LQ corresponded to x2 and x4 compression factors compared to HQ, using CRF values of 0, 17, and 34 (applied to video only). Distances were presented in fixed order (near to far), and each sequence lasted 30 seconds.

After being administered a Consent Form, and a Demographic & Background Questionnaire, the test conditions started. A basic Unity3D scenario was recreated for the viewing conditions, following the recommendations from ITU-R BT.500-13 [11], as done in e.g. [4, 8]. Likewise, an in-session quality rating method was adopted, as suggested and successfully validated in recent works [4]. The participants were standing up during the test on a comfortable room with no surrounding noise and external distractions (see Fig. 3), and used a Meta Quest 3 headset, connected to a GPU-powered laptop. They were asked to not move (so 3DoF+ viewing), and no playback interactions were allowed, but the sequences

were displayed in a linear mode. The experiment lasted between 20-25 min for each participant.

Fig. 2. Resulting video quality for the encoded sequences at HQ (left, requiring 9Mbps bandwidth), MQ (centre, requiring 4Mbps, and LQ (right, requiring 1 Mbps)

After a brief training sequence, participants viewed the three quality levels in counter-balanced order and responded to both SSM (absolute, 10-point Likert scale) and DSM (relative, 5-point scale) questions using the VR controller. This combined method helps assess users’ satisfaction with maximum quality and their perception of degradation versus the reference, considering the limitations of current volumetric video. The process was repeated for each distance (D1, D2, D3), and final general questions were completed on paper to avoid extending the VR session.

IV. RESULTS

A. Test 1 Results

Test 1 results show a clear performance gap between V*-PCC and G-PCC. V*-PCC maintained consistent voxel density (~1.1 million points) across quality levels (HQ, MQ, LQ) due to its image-based design, which offloads color and geometry processing to the GPU. Since pixels are independent, processing time remains stable as long as the data fits the video frame. In contrast, G-PCC’s performance depends heavily on voxel density and distribution, as it uses hierarchical structures (e.g., octrees) for geometry compression. As point density increases, processing becomes slower and potentially unsuitable for real-time use. G-PCC showed a sharp drop in voxel count as compression increased averaging 203,720 at HQ, and falling below 20% of the original resolution at medium and low levels. This variability limits its suitability for adaptive volumetric streaming. In contrast, V*-PCC maintained consistent performance: FPS remained stable across quality levels (14.7–15, matching capture rate), whereas G-PCC showed greater fluctuation lower at HQ (10.18 FPS), but able to sustain 15 FPS at lower qualities (see Fig. 3).

The most notable difference was in processing time. The V*-PCC pipeline consistently achieved low processing times (7.89–8.61 ms), while G-PCC showed much higher values especially at HQ (93.5 ms) and even at LQ (17.8 ms), which was still twice as high as V*-PCC. These results confirm that V*-PCC offers better processing efficiency and stable fidelity, making it more suitable for real-time and adaptive volumetric video. Notably, G-PCC only supports real-time performance (<15 FPS) for point clouds above 30K points due to its high processing cost, whereas V*-PCC can maintain 30 FPS even

with dense point clouds (1 million points in Test 1), justifying its selection for Test 2. Test 1 served as a functional benchmark against G-PCC under controlled conditions to validate real-time capability, fidelity, and efficiency before deployment in Test 2. Although a fixed content scenario was used here, future work will expand the analysis to include more sequences, motion dynamics, and metrics.

Fig. 3. FPS comparison in Test 1 (Blue: G-PCC; Orange: V*-PCC).

B. Test 2 Results

A total of 24 participants (13 male, 11 female), aged 21 to 62, took part in the experiment. While both SSM and DSM are standardized and commonly used in QoE research, their combined application here strengthens methodological rigor. SSM offers absolute quality ratings per condition, while DSM captures relative differences against a reference. This dual-method approach provides a more complete view of user perception, aligns with recent state-of-the-art evaluations [1, 3, 6], and enhances cross-study comparability. Though not novel individually, their integration in a controlled VR setting across multiple distances and compression levels adds reliability and detail to the results.

DSM Results: With respect to DSM methodology, participants’ responses varied according to compression levels and observation distances, as expected. At D1 (Fig. 4), participants showed strong sensitivity to compression. HQ was rated “Equivalent” by 72%, and “Slightly Better” by only 8%, possibly due to expressive gestures or prior exposure to lower-quality sequences. MQ received 40% “Equivalent” and 52% “Worse” ratings, indicating moderate penalization. LQ scored lowest, with 84% of responses being “Slightly Worse” or “Much Worse”. At D2 (Fig. 5), HQ remained well rated (52% “Equivalent”, 16% “Better”), while MQ followed closely (48% “Equivalent”, 16% “Better”). LQ improved slightly but still had 76% of responses in “Worse” categories.

At D3 (Fig. 6), quality differences were less noticeable. HQ, MQ, and LQ received 60%, 52%, and 48% “Equivalent” ratings, respectively, suggesting increased tolerance to degradation with distance. A small proportion (up to 16% for HQ, 12% for MQ) rated the sequences as “Slightly Better” or more. In general, DSM results showed that HQ was consistently rated high, MQ followed a similar but slightly lower trend, and LQ showed clear perceptual improvement as

distance increased, which aligns with prior findings in related studies [5, 7, 8].

To confirm the impact of distance and compression levels on perceived quality, a two-way ANOVA was conducted on all collected scores. The statistical results ($F(2, 207) = 4.17$ for distance, $p = 0.017$; $F(2, 207) = 41.93$ for quality, $p < 0.001$) confirmed that both distance and quality had statistically significant effects on the perceived quality. Furthermore, a significant interaction effect between distance and quality was found ($F(4, 207) = 4.73$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that the influence of compression varies depending on the proximity to the target volumetric video sequence. These findings are illustrated in Fig. 7, which shows the mean ratings for each condition along with 95% Confidence Intervals. Notably, HQ consistently outperformed MQ and LQ across all distances, although MQ showed a clear dip at D1 (mean = 2.38), followed by an increase at D2 (2.58) and D3 (2.83). LQ followed a similar upward trend but remained lower overall. These results suggest that perceptual differences were most pronounced at closer distances, and became less distinct as the viewing distance increased, particularly between MQ and LQ.

Fig. 7. Mean user ratings by distance and quality level in Test 2.

SSM Results: With respect to the SSM methodology results, several findings can be remarked (Fig. 8). On the one hand, the absolute 1–10 ratings for the three quality sequences were generally aligned with the trends observed from the DSM results. HQ sequences received consistently high ratings across all distance levels (though not reaching the “Excellent” threshold). MQ began to receive better scores at the D2 and D3 distance levels, and a clearer separation emerged between D1, D2, and D3 in the case of LQ. On the other hand, it can be observed that quality differences between HQ, MQ, and LQ were more evident at D1, while at D2 the difference was primarily noticeable for LQ, and at D3 all three sequences received more similar ratings, especially MQ and LQ. To confirm these perceptual trends, a two-way ANOVA was conducted on the SSM scores.

The analysis showed significant effects for Quality ($F(2, 207) = 193.47$, $p < 0.001$), Distance ($F(2, 207) = 35.74$, $p < 0.001$), and their interaction ($F(4, 207) = 21.44$, $p < 0.001$) confirming that perceived quality is influenced by both factors. Tukey’s HSD post-hoc test revealed that at D1, all quality levels differed significantly ($p < 0.001$); at D2, HQ–LQ and MQ–LQ were significant ($p < 0.05$), but not HQ–MQ; and at D3, no significant differences were found ($p > 0.1$).

Fig. 4. DSM Likert rating distribution for D1 in Test 2.

Fig. 5. DSM Likert rating Distribution for D2 in Test 2.

Fig. 6. DSM Likert rating distribution for D3 in Test 2.

Fig. 8. Boxplot of SSM quality rating by distance and quality level in Test 2.

Overall Perceived Quality and Impact: After the VR experience, participants answered three post-test questions on the perceptual quality and potential use of the high-quality reference sequences. Q1 stated: “In general, for the maximum

quality level (reference sequences), the quality difference between the three distances has been noticeable”. As shown in Fig. 10, most participants (79%) agreed that even at maximum quality, distance affected perception. For Q2, 66% agreed the reference sequences provided satisfactory quality for an immersive experience. These results confirm that the high-quality encoding level was generally sufficient to support perceptual immersion in the given context. Q3 stated: “When referred to the maximum quality (reference sequences), the achieved video quality can already have an impact in the immersive media consumption or communication sector”. As show in Fig. 10, while 52% expressed agreement, a notable portion (36%) selected “Neutral,” reflecting a degree of uncertainty. This may suggest that while the quality is promising, users remain cautious about its readiness for broader deployment, possibly due to other system-level constraints (e.g., hardware, content type, or interaction limitations).

Fig. 9. Participants opinions on Q1, Q2 and Q3 in Test 2.

Fig.10. Perceived quality difference between sequences at each distance in Test 2.

Finally, to complement the results, participants were asked if quality differences between the three sequences were noticeable at each distance. As shown in Fig. 11, responses followed a distance-dependent trend: most agreed at D1, fewer at D2, and most disagreed at D3 confirming that perceptual sensitivity to compression decreases with distance.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This study assessed the performance and perceptual quality of a novel V*-PCC codec when encoding and visualizing dynamic sequences of volumetric human holograms, using a two-part experimentation phase: (i) a technical comparison with G-PCC; (ii) a user-centered perceptual evaluation to gain insights into the impact of compression levels and viewing distances, in a combined manner. On the one hand, the objective performance results confirm the potential of the newly developed codec and support its adoption for running

the associated QoE experiment. On the other hand, the results from the perceptual quality experiment confirm the impact of compression levels on the QoE at different distance levels. Compression artifacts were noticed at close distance, less noticeable at medium distance, and became almost unnoticeable at far distance. Indeed, low quality (LQ) encoded sequences obtained comparable quality ratings across all considered distances. These findings provide preliminary but meaningful insights, laying the groundwork for continued research in this domain. Nonetheless, the present results should be interpreted with caution, as the study was conducted using a single capture setup, a fixed 3DoF+ viewing mode, and a short-term evaluation protocol. These limitations may restrict generalizability to real-world scenarios involving prolonged use, varied hardware, interactive conditions, or different forms of immersive content.

Future work will include more diverse and granular QoE studies to determine perceptual thresholds across a broader range of distances, content types, and user profiles. Likewise, comparative evaluations with additional volumetric video codecs and more diverse scene dynamics will be explored. Furthermore, the insights from these studies will be applied to devise and evaluate novel distance-aware adaptive volumetric video streaming pipelines.

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